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Telomerase modulation during cellular senescence.

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Cellular senescence was characterized by modulation of the enzyme that maintains the integrity of the chromosomal DNA at the 3' ends, telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT).

Results

We studied changes in telomerase reverse transcriptase expression associated with cell populations from young humans with either high or low proliferative potential to identify genes that distinguish the transcriptomes of proliferative or senescent cell populations.

Figure 1: Using a fibroblast population with low proliferative potential to identify senescence-associated genes revealed activation of TERT during senescence.

n=4 fibroblasts from young adults (females): high proliferative capacity

n=5 fibroblasts from young adults (females): low proliferative capacity

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
20297	0.0471446	-2.3133277	-3.83474	-0.38280382	TERT	5354/45015	88.1

When comparing cells that were matched for age (i.e., querying senescence-associated transcriptional characteristics in a cell population that was age-matched, rather than identifying senescence-associated features by comparing young (proliferative) and senescent populations based on difference in age, TERT expression was transcriptionally induced when proliferative capacity was low.

Figure 2: Expression of a ligand for an exhaustion receptor, PD-L1, the ligand for PD1 (PDCD1) is sufficient to activate TERT expression.

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFoldChange	Gene	Rank	%DE
56928	1.74E-03	-4.4190804	-0.870373	-0.8946739	TERT	409/62976	99.4

The data suggested an intrinsic link between exhaustion and senescence programs.

Discussion

We described here activation of the telomerase reverse transcriptome (TERT) as a defining transcriptional characteristic of a fibroblast population with low proliferative potential, and provided evidence suggesting an intrinsic link between exhaustion and senescence programs.

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Methods

We studied total expression in human cells to study senescence and exhaustion using RNA-sequencing and microarray datasets (GSE100824 and GSE185679; published) in conjunction with R-based computational methods.